

Instability of Ostrogradsky Formalism and Stability Conditions in Non-Inertial Physics

Timur F. Kamalov

Department of Physics and Mathematics,
State University of Education (formerly Moscow Region State
University, RF)
timkamalov@gmail.com

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Abstract

We examine the role of stability conditions in higher-derivative dynamics arising in non-inertial reference frames. The non-negativity of the second variation of the action selects dynamically admissible trajectories within the Ostrogradsky framework and generates an additional contribution to the Hamilton–Jacobi equation. When the wave function is written in the Madelung form, this term coincides with the Bohm quantum potential. The result provides a compact correspondence between non-inertial (higher-derivative) corrections and the mathematical structure of quantum dynamics, without modifying Newtonian mechanics or introducing additional postulates.

1 Stability Condition

We consider an action functional depending on time derivatives up to order N ,

$$S[q] = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}, \dots, q^{(N)}, t) dt. \quad (1)$$

Variation of the action yields the Euler–Ostrogradsky equations,

$$\sum_{k=0}^N (-1)^k \frac{d^k}{dt^k} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial q^{(k)}} \right) = 0, \quad (2)$$

whose solutions are known to exhibit the well-documented Ostrogradsky instability [1].

To isolate dynamically admissible trajectories, we impose an additional *stability condition* requiring the second variation to be non-negative:

$$\delta^2 S \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

A related formulation was previously discussed in [2]. This mathematical condition selects a subset of stable trajectories within the otherwise unstable higher-derivative dynamics introduced by Ostrogradsky [3], the second variation may be written as

$$\delta^2 S = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \sum_{i,j=0}^N \delta q^{(i)} \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial q^{(i)} \partial q^{(j)}} \delta q^{(j)} dt. \quad (4)$$

The associated Jacobi–Ostrogradsky operator is

$$\mathcal{J}[q] = \sum_{i,j=0}^N (-1)^{i+j} \frac{d^i}{dt^i} \left(\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial q^{(i)} \partial q^{(j)}} \right) \frac{d^j}{dt^j}, \quad (5)$$

and the stability condition amounts to the requirement that this operator be non-negative on admissible variations. This mathematical constraint selects a subset of stable solutions within the otherwise unstable higher-derivative dynamics.

2 Extended Dynamics in Non-Inertial Frames

2.1 General Structure

Real physical reference frames are never perfectly inertial: small uncontrolled accelerations, environmental fluctuations, and random fields introduce additional inertial forces. To account for these effects we consider a kinematic transformation from an idealized inertial frame to a non-inertial frame containing small stochastic accelerations.

The dynamics in such frames naturally acquire additional terms that depend on higher time derivatives of the coordinate, reflecting the presence of non-inertial forces rather than modifications of Newtonian mechanics. In this sense, the extended dynamical equations represent the inertial-force contributions associated with the non-inertial frame.

2.2 Stochastic Non-Inertial Frames

Let $q(t)$ denote the inertial coordinate and let $q'(t)$ be the coordinate measured in a non-inertial frame undergoing small, rapidly fluctuating accelerations. Following [2], we express the transformation as a Taylor series:

$$q'(t) = q(t) + \dot{q}(t)\tau + \sum_{k=2}^N \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \tau^k q^{(k)}(t), \quad (6)$$

where τ is a small characteristic time scale associated with the averaging over random inertial fluctuations. For microscopic systems one may choose $\tau = \hbar/(2mc^2)$.

The additional terms in (6) encode the influence of non-inertial accelerations and provide a systematic expansion of stochastic inertial effects.

2.3 Extended Dynamical Equation

Applying transformation (6) to Newton's second law in the inertial frame and retaining contributions from the transformed accelerations yields an extended dynamical equation of the form:

$$F - ma + \tau m \dot{a} - \frac{1}{2}\tau^2 m a^{(2)} + \dots + (-1)^n \frac{1}{n!} \tau^n m a^{(n)} + \dots = 0. \quad (7)$$

The additional higher-derivative terms in (7) represent *non-inertial contributions* arising from the fluctuating frame. They do not modify Newtonian mechanics; rather, they reflect the fact that the observer resides in a frame with small stochastic accelerations.

2.4 Recovery of the Inertial Limit

Averaging over the random components of the non-inertial frame removes the higher-derivative contributions:

$$\langle a^{(k)} \rangle = 0, \quad k \geq 1, \quad (8)$$

and equation (7) reduces to the standard Newtonian form,

$$F = ma. \quad (9)$$

Thus Newton's second law is recovered as the limiting case of vanishing non-inertial fluctuations, while the extended structure (7) provides a systematic description of small inertial-force effects in stochastic or non-inertial reference frames.

3 Hamilton–Jacobi Structure and Emergent Quantum Dynamics

Higher-derivative terms generated by non-inertial fluctuations modify the classical action and lead to an extended Hamilton–Jacobi (HJ) description. In this section we show that the stability condition introduced above produces an additional contribution in the HJ equation, and that this term coincides with the well-known Bohm potential when the wave function is written in the Madelung form.

3.1 Action Phase and Derivative Expansion

Let $S(t)$ denote the classical action. In a non-inertial frame with a small characteristic timescale τ , we expand the action in higher time derivatives,

$$S(t) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{S^{(n)}(t)}{n!} \tau^n, \quad (10)$$

and define a complex phase in the standard way,

$$\psi = R e^{iS/\hbar}, \quad (11)$$

where $R \geq 0$ is the amplitude. The parameter τ encodes non-inertial fluctuations and introduces higher-derivative contributions to the phase dynamics.

3.2 Extended Hamilton–Jacobi Equation

In the presence of non-inertial effects, the classical Hamilton–Jacobi equation acquires an additional term,

$$-\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = \frac{(\nabla S)^2}{2m} + V(q, \dot{q}) + Q(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}, \dots), \quad (12)$$

where Q originates from the higher-derivative contributions selected by the stability condition $\delta^2 S \geq 0$. The explicit form of Q depends on the details of the non-inertial fluctuations but remains real and transforms as a scalar under coordinate reparametrizations.

3.3 Connection with the Schrödinger Equation

Consider the Madelung representation [4] of the time-dependent Schrödinger equation,

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi. \quad (13)$$

Substituting $\psi = Re^{iS/\hbar}$ into (13) and separating real and imaginary parts yields two coupled equations:

1. the continuity equation,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left(\rho \frac{\nabla S}{m} \right) = 0, \quad (14)$$

where $\rho = R^2$;

2. the quantum Hamilton–Jacobi equation,

$$-\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = \frac{(\nabla S)^2}{2m} + V + Q_B, \quad (15)$$

with the Bohm potential Q_B [5].

$$Q_B = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 R}{R}. \quad (16)$$

3.4 Identification of the Non-Inertial Term

Comparison of (12) and (15) shows that the additional term in the extended Hamilton–Jacobi equation is mathematically equivalent to the Bohm potential,

$$Q(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}, \dots) \simeq Q_B = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 R}{R}. \quad (17)$$

Thus the Bohm potential appears naturally as a consequence of the stability condition when higher-derivative (non-inertial) corrections are included. This correspondence suggests that certain quantum-mechanical features may be interpreted as manifestations of non-inertial effects encoded in the higher-derivative structure of the action.

4 Path-Integral and Stochastic Interpretation

The presence of higher time derivatives in non-inertial dynamics suggests a natural connection with path-integral and stochastic formulations of quantum mechanics. In a non-inertial frame the fluctuations of the coordinate and its derivatives generate a continuous family of nearby trajectories, and the stability condition selects those trajectories whose second variation remains non-negative.

4.1 Fluctuating Trajectories

Let $q(t)$ denote an admissible trajectory and let $\eta(t)$ represent a small stochastic fluctuation induced by the non-inertial frame,

$$q(t) \longrightarrow q(t) + \eta(t), \quad \langle \eta(t) \rangle = 0. \quad (18)$$

In a frame with small random accelerations, $\eta(t)$ is not an ordinary perturbation but possesses higher-order correlations,

$$\langle \eta^{(k)}(t) \eta^{(m)}(t') \rangle \neq 0, \quad k, m \geq 1, \quad (19)$$

reflecting the influence of fluctuating inertial forces.

All such trajectories contribute to the effective action through the second variation $\delta^2 S$, and the stability condition serves to restrict the physically admissible fluctuations.

4.2 Relation to the Path Integral

In the Feynman path integral formulation [6] the transition amplitude is formally written as

$$\mathcal{A}(q_b, t_b; q_a, t_a) = \int \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} S[q]\right) \mathcal{D}q. \quad (20)$$

Higher-derivative contributions modify the phase $S[q]$ in a way that depends on the non-inertial characteristics of the frame. The dominant contributions to the integral correspond to paths for which the second variation $\delta^2 S$ is non-negative, since paths with $\delta^2 S < 0$ are exponentially suppressed.

Thus the stability condition may be viewed as selecting the subset of paths that contribute constructively to the transition amplitude in the semiclassical limit. This provides a consistent interpretation of the extended Hamilton–Jacobi structure in terms of weighted fluctuations in path space.

4.3 Stochastic Analogy

There is also an analogy with stochastic mechanics, in which the particle position is modeled as a diffusion process,

$$dq(t) = v(t) dt + \sqrt{2D} dW(t), \quad (21)$$

where $W(t)$ is a Wiener process. In the present approach the role of the diffusion is played by inertial fluctuations induced by the non-inertial frame, with the effective diffusion constant determined by the small timescale τ . This structure resembles stochastic mechanics [7].

The combination of the deterministic drift $v(t)$ and the stochastic fluctuations leads to an effective potential term in the Hamilton–Jacobi equation. The form of this term coincides with the Bohm potential Q_B when expressed via the Madelung variables.

4.4 Interpretation

The path–integral and stochastic viewpoints therefore provide a natural interpretation of the term Q appearing in the extended Hamilton–Jacobi equation. In both frameworks Q represents the collective effect of fluctuations of nearby paths generated by non-inertial accelerations. When the wave function is expressed in polar form, this term reduces to the Bohm potential, linking the stability condition of higher-derivative systems with standard quantum dynamics.

5 Conclusion

We have examined higher–derivative dynamics in non-inertial reference frames and formulated a stability condition requiring the stationarity of the action together with the non-negativity of its second variation. Within Ostrogradsky’s framework this condition selects a subclass of dynamically admissible trajectories and yields an extended Hamilton–Jacobi equation containing an additional real term Q originating from non-inertial (higher-derivative) effects.

When the wave function is expressed in the Madelung form, the same term appears as the Bohm potential of standard quantum mechanics. This correspondence indicates that certain features usually viewed as quantum-mechanical may also be interpreted as arising from inertial fluctuations encoded in higher derivatives of the action.

The path–integral and stochastic perspectives both support this interpretation: the stability condition restricts the contributions in path space to trajectories with non-negative second variation, while the effective fluctuations in non-inertial frames lead to the appearance of a quantum-like potential term.

Although the analysis presented here is classical in origin, it suggests a structural connection between non-inertial corrections and the mathematical form of quantum evolution. Further work may clarify how these ideas extend to field-theoretic systems and whether the stability condition can be expressed directly in a covariant setting.

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